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Third **S**erbian **R**adiation **O**ncology **C**ongress

Abstract book

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Ethno Complex Vrđnickska kula, Vrđnik**

BrachyTerra project Serbia

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Cervical cancer is 4th most common cancer among women, with an estimated 604 000 new cases and 342 000 deaths in 2020. About 90% of new cases and deaths worldwide in 2020 occurred in low- and middle-income countries. It is 4th most common cancer among women in Serbia, after breast, lung and colorectal cancer, with 1087 new cases in 2020 and 5th most common cause of cancer death in Serbia, with standardized cancer mortality rates 10,7 and 453 deaths. Radiation therapy is the main treatment modality for locally advanced cervical cancer. In addition to teletherapy, brachytherapy boost plays a key role in dose escalation to the tumor volume. BrachyTerra is a non-profit learning platform. It is based on voluntary work of experts on cervix cancer radiotherapy. With conventional brachytherapy local control of cervix cancer is 75-95% in early and 30-65% in advanced tumors. With MRI guided brachytherapy local control is 98% to 90%, with low morbidity (EMBRACE – I study). CT guided brachytherapy is a low-cost alternative to MRI approach. This course is designed for radiation oncologists, medical physicists, and radiological technologists from Serbia and invited countries to assist in the implementation of MRI and CT planning for cervical cancer brachytherapy.

Keywords: Cervica cancer, Brachytherapy, learning platform, Brachy-Terra

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